

TRANSFERRING RESOURCE REVENUES INTO HUMAN CAPITAL IN POST-SOVIET COUNTRIES

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Abstract

Natural resources are depleting faster as human demand growing rapidly and will be vanished shortly as it is non-replaceable recourse. The only way to benefit in this process is to invest natural resource revenues into human capital. This study investigates education role in HDI and in development in resource-rich CIS countries, particularly Russia, Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan and how education reforms in these countries contributed to HDI level and economic prosperity. This paper realized that these three countries have more commonality not only economic field, but also in education sphere. Government dominant financing of primary and secondary education, similar level of compulsory education, literacy level, little R&D budget, similar reforms in exams, which contributed similar Education Index Level and eventually very close HDI scores. The paper concludes that despite huge accrued oil revenues and their usage in government budget in these countries, education expenses part did not increase in last decade and still below average of EU and OECD countries. However, oil revenues did let governments to invest into non-oil sector, including education sector. More than reforms especially in salary by performance, petro-dollars went into building educational infrastructure such as schools, training centers.

Keywords: Human Capital, HDI, Post-Soviet Countries, Resource Rich Countries, Education Index
JEL: H52, I28, O13, O15

Introduction

Knowledge society is a megatrend formed by information and technology which derived by development of all components of 4th industrial revolution. Since globalization swept away complexity of reaching knowledge even for LDCs, evaluation of human capital now based on high speed, big data, and artificial intelligence. Education had been always at the center of theories of development, and welfare. Therefore, countries reaching to knowledge society level as development strategy investing in education in context of human capital.

It is obvious that, GDP no longer assess progress of fundamental prosperity of society accurately. However, *Inclusive Wealth Index* launched by UN contains produced capital, natural capital and human capital for 140 countries much precise which in line of UN Sustainable Development Goals. The index conveys that human capital grew in every country between 1992 and 2014 and is the key reason that equalizes the decline in natural capital in most countries.

Since 1990, HDI consist of *long and healthy life, knowledge, and decent standard of living indices* with equal weight. (UNDP, 2010, p.215) Four indicators are currently employed to formulate Global HDI, which are life expectancy at birth as representing *health*; and Gross National Income per capita by purchasing power parity

as representing *standard of living* and two sub-indicators like mean years of schooling of population of ages 25 and over, and expected years of schooling for children as representing *education*. Before 2010, adult literacy was weighted at one of third and school attendance at two of third to differ a person with two years of schooling and high qualification of study. But since then, the new introduced indicator “mean years of schooling” better reveals the educational achievements of people 25 years and above and so better differ between high HDI countries and only high literacy level countries (UNDP,2015, p. 5-11). HDI is under spotlight of Sustainable Development Goals established by WB which is intention to reach for all countries until 2030. In this report, *Life expectancy* considered as SDG 3, *Expected years of schooling* as SDG4.3, *Mean years of schooling* as SDG4.6, *GNI per capita* as SDG 8.5 (UNDP, 2018).

Unlike capitalist system, overall economy dominated by public sector in Soviet Union member countries in 69 years. In this planned economic system education also considered as pure public good not only in elementary school level which rose questions about efficiency and efficacy of education system. Just after getting independence, reforms started in most sectors including education system and transferring into contemporary education system with presence of private education institutions, adopting capitalist rules in education financing and businesses also.

Literature Review in human capital impacts

Human capital is the sum of knowledge and skills contained by the labor force. This knowledge that the labor force gets is mainly formulated through education, which gives people the ability to increase productivity. As an engine of economic growth, raising human capital should be at the center of government policies.

Education has been considered as a key part of human capital and is often cited as an important factor of economic growth and development (Romer 1990; Jurges & Schneider 2004, Barro, 1991, 2001). Schultz (1963) points out that increasing education level of labors is a key part of growth both in developing and developed world.

Becker (1964) pointed out that investments in human capital raise productivity and earnings of individuals as highly educated and healthier labor force is relatively more productive. Engelbrecht (1997) considers human capital as an important input of growth theories. Empirical studies also confirm human capital crucial for economic growth (see, e.g., Schultz, 1961; Becker, 1964; Uzawa, 1965; Rosen, 1976; Hicks, 1980; Romer, 1986; Murphy et al., 1991; Barro, 1991; Levine & Renelt, 1992; Barro & Lee, 1993; Krueger & Lindahl, 2001; Klasen (2002), Baldacci et al., 2004, Van Leeuwen & Foldvari, 2008) among others.

Effects of public education expenditures have been extensively discussed in the literature of economic growth. Many researchers concluded that the government education expenditure promotes the economic growth. (See Barro (1991), Levine & Renelt (1992), Easterly & Rebelo (1993), Sachs & Warner (1995), Devarajan, Swaroop & Zou (1996), Zhang & Casagrande (1998) and Blankenau, Simpson & Tomljanovich (2007), Bils & Klenow (2000), Krueger & Lindahl (2001), Rangazas (2002), Cohen & Soto (2007), Lutz et al.(2008), Kaboski (2009), Hanushek & Woessmann (2012).

Otani and Villanueva (1993) found that education programs and human capital investments increase economic output and per capita income in fifty-five developing countries during 1970 to 1985 years. Azariadis & Drazen (1990) realized that countries with higher literacy rates demonstrated higher economic growth than other countries among 71 countries.

Wide range of studies finds a positive effect of public education expenditures on growth (Landau (1983, 1986), Barro (1991), Benhabib & Spiegel (1994), Barro & Sala-i-Martin (1995), Sala-i-Martin (1997a, 1997b), Stroup & Heckelman (2001), Afonso & Jalles (2013) Zhang & Casagrande (1998), Baldacci et al. (2008), Jung & Thorbeck (2003), Rehme (2007), Zhang (1997), among others)

However, Devarajan et al. (1996) found negative association between education expenditures and economic growth in most of their estimates for 43 developing countries over twenty years. Results of Patrinos&Psacharopoulos (2002), Nurudeen&Usman (2010) and some other studies are in this line. On the other hand, Levine &Renelt (1992), Blis&Klenov (2000) Ansari & Singh (1997) confirmed that there is too weak evidence of a relationship between government education programs with economic growth.

Some studies looking at the connection between economic growth and education expenditures have supported a bidirectional link between these variables in a short run, which means government education expenditures support economic growth and economic growth in its turn increase education level in the economy (Afzal et.al. (2010), Cullison (1993) and Barro (2001), Zhang &Casagrande (1998), Lin (2003), Tamang (2011), Baldacci et al (2008), Ogujiuba&Adeniyi (2005), Jorgenson &Fraumeni (1992), Chandra (2010),Owusu-Nantwi (2015), Hussin et.al., (2012), Bose et.al, (2003), Basu&Bhattarai (2009), Parmani (2009), Okubal (2005), Al-Yousif(2005), Blankenau&Simpson (2003), Bose et.al, (2003), Basu&Bhattarai (2009), Lee (2012) among others. Pradhan (2009) and Tang (2009) found only one-way positive impact of economic growth on government education expenditures.

Fiszbein&Psacharopoulos (1992) also found positive impact of education expenditures on economic growth in Venezuela case. The study reveals that investments in primary education have the highest impact on economic growth whereas higher education investments exhibit the least impact among the three levels of education. Qi (2016) taking into account different educational levels reveal that in general, government education expenditure has significantly positive impact on economic growth in China, especially Government education expenditure in below high-education has positive impact on local economic growth, whereas the effect of education expenditure in high-education is insignificant. The estimates of Carmignani (2016) show that for every dollar the government spends on education, GDP grows on average by \$20 for each of 151 countries. In order to reduce the risk of reverse causality, the study indicates that countries that spent (1% point of GDP) more on education in 1990s experienced (0.9% point of GDP) faster growth in the subsequent decade.

The results of Musila&Belassi (2004) suggest that a 1% increase in average education expenditure per worker will lead to about 0.04% increase in economic output in the short run and by about 0.6% in the long run for Uganda during the period 1965-1999.

It is understandable that unlike other elements of HDI, education can be expected to be value added on the economy in long run. Considering the fact indicating primary education has most impact on economy, one can be concluded that, education associates with growth in a long run. Using a meta-analysis of 237 estimates drawn from 29 primary studies, Churchill, Ugur& Yew (2017) found the effect of government education expenditure on growth is positive for developed countries, but statistically insignificant for less developed countries. Out of these studies, 14 reports show a positive and statistically significant effect, 12 reports show a negative effect, and 3 reports had no statistically significant effects of government education expenditure on growth. As a part of this research Churchill, Ugur & Yew (2015) using a sample of 306 estimates drawn from 31 papers, find that unlike health expenditures, the effect of government education expenditure on growth is positive. However, combined effects of government expenditure on both education and health altogether as representing government human capital expenditures, outcomes show a growth effect.

Education can affect growth through different channels. For instance, Glomm&Ravikumar (1992) find that income inequality declines more quickly under public education, and private education generates greater per capita incomes. Annabi et al (2011) reveal that education increases the rate of capital accumulation and labor force. Levy & Clements (1996) education has a significant effect on private investment. Hong-Sang & Thorbecke (2003) and Grubb & Michelson (1974) pointed out that well-targeted education expenditure not only increase economic growth but can be effective in reducing poverty.

Zhang (1996, 1997) find that public educational subsidy through lowering the cost of educating increases the private education expenditure that stimulates long-run economic growth and reduces welfare losses. According to U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, full-time workers with advanced degrees had 3.3 times more median weekly earnings than workers without high school diploma and more than twice than workers with high school and college diploma which associates with unemployment rate (4 times less) among education level persons age 25 or older (Torpey, 2018). Jackson, Johnson & Persico (2015) show that a 10% increase in per-pupil spending each year for all 12 grades in US public schools leads to 0.27 more completed years of education, 7.25 % higher wages, and a 3.67 % reduction in the annual incidence of adult poverty. DeBaun, B., & Roc, M. (2013) estimates that a 5% increase in the national high school graduation rate for male students alone, would save \$19.7 billion annually in USA. Report reveals that the national average for educating a student is \$12,643 per year while average cost of inmate is more than double that amount, at \$28,323. Barnett (1996) reveals that children who did not participate in the preschool program were 70% more likely to be arrested for a violent crime by age eighteen. This study resulted that children out of this program multiplied by five times the risk that they would become chronic lawbreakers as adults. Lochner (2011) resulted that education can reduce crime and mortality rates, improve health, and increase political participation. Gupta et al (2001) have studied the impact of government expenditures on education and health in developing economies in 50 countries and found that increase in government expenditure in education and health can decrease a number of child deaths. And the impact of education is more powerful than health in this regard. Hansson & Henrekson (1994) found that unlike government consumptions, expenditures on education have a positive impact on growth. Emanuele Baldacci et al., (2008) found that 1% (as of GDP) increase in public education expenses result in 3 more years of schooling on average and foster economic growth by 1.4%. Furthermore, 1% (as of GDP) increase in public health expenses improves under-5 years child mortality rate by 0.6 and increases the GDP per capita growth by 0.5 %.

Global experience of education as human capital

The primary, secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education levels always had been dominated by public funding in OECD countries. By the end of 20th century, government education expenditures in many developing countries approached to the average of developed countries, which brought down education inequality for all age groups and in all world regions. However unlike in low-income countries, high-income countries households` share of education expenditures at tertiary education level more than at lower levels (Roser & Ortiz-Ospina, 2018).

More than 90% of all children enrolled in elementary and secondary school in the US go to public schools mainly financed by state and local governments. However, in France public primary schools financed by national government for free to reduce inequality among regions which was in private hands before 1883 (Lindert, 2004; Roser & Ortiz-Ospina, 2018).

Almost 80% of education expenditures (5.47% of GDP) financed by US government, while private education expenses stood at 1.38% of GDP in 2015 (Roser & Ortiz-Ospina, 2018). Public and private spending in educational institutions does not even account for 10 % of OECD countries` total GDP (Temple, 2002: 58). According to Eurostat data, Public expenditure on health in the EU increased steeply between 2003-2017 years and is now the second highest government expenditure with share above 15% (7% of GDP), while public expenditure towards education slightly decreased from 10.9% of budget expenses in 2007 into 10.2% in 2017. In Africa, Asia, and Latin America the incidence of investments in primary education is high, but this ratio is low in OECD countries. (Patrinos & Psacharopoulos, 2002)

Education expenditures in France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Spain, Luxembourg, Italy, Greece and Portugal are mainly covered by the central government on a general budget, as in Turkey. In Germany, Austria, Belgium and the UK, it is covered by local governments. In Sweden, Denmark and Finland, education expenditure has been covered by public and local governments, but responsibility has been passed on to local governments (Egeli & Hayrulloğlu, 2014: 99).

On average, expenditure on secondary education is 1.2 times greater than expenditure on primary education. This ratio reaches or exceeds 1.5 in the Czech Republic, France, Hungary and the Netherlands, but is lower than 1 in Denmark, Iceland, Indonesia, Poland, Slovenia and Turkey. Similarly, educational institutions in OECD countries spend an average of 1.8 times more on each tertiary student than they do on each primary student. However, spending patterns vary widely, mainly because education policies vary more at the tertiary level. For example, Canada, France, Hungary, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Sweden, Turkey and USA spend between 2.2 and 2.6 times more on a tertiary student than on a primary student, but Brazil and Mexico spend 3 times as much. In OECD countries, overall expenditure per student by educational institutions from primary to tertiary levels of education averages 27% of per capita GDP, broken down into 22% of per capita GDP at primary level, 25% at lower secondary level, 25% at upper secondary level and 40% at tertiary level (OECD, 2017)

In France, Norway, Switzerland and the United Kingdom, 60% or more of growth in GDP is generated by those with tertiary education. (OECD, 2012)

In 2016, general government expenditure on 'education' in the EU-28 amounted to 4.7 % of GDP. Of this, 'pre-primary and primary education' accounted for 1.5 % of GDP and secondary education accounted for 1.9 % of GDP. For tertiary education, an average of 0.7 % of GDP was reported. As a percentage of GDP, the highest amounts were reported by Iceland (7.1 % of GDP), Denmark (6.9 %), followed by Sweden (6.6 % of GDP) and Belgium (6.4 % of GDP). For Lithuania, Cyprus as well as Iceland and Switzerland, education expenditure accounted for over 15 % of total expenditure. The lowest ratios of total expenditure were observed for Italy (7.9 % of total expenditure) and Greece (8.6 %).

At the level of the EU-28, government expenditure on 'education' as a ratio to GDP remained relatively stable over the 2002-2016 period, decreasing by 0.3 pp. from 5.0 % of GDP in 2002 to 4.7 % of GDP in 2016. However, since overall government expenditure as a ratio to GDP increased by 2.7 pp. (notably in the functions 'health' and 'social protection'), the share of expenditure on education in total expenditure decreased from 11.1 % in 2002 to 10.2 % in 2016. US spends highest in education among all the developed countries.

There are now 75 million children caught up in conflict and humanitarian crises who need educational support and most of them will continue to experience educational disruptions. Only one in four of the world's child refugees will receive a secondary education, and just 1% will go on to higher education (Brown, 2018).

Chart 1. Role of Human Capital in GDP

Source: UNITED NATIONS DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME (UNDP), Human Development Reports

According to World Bank classification, Azerbaijan, Russia and Kazakhstan considered as upper-middle income countries. (WB, 2019) As can be seen from given chart above, Human Capital accounted 76% of World GDP in 1995, especially very high for high income countries (OECD) and highest for all type of countries comparing with natural and produced capital. Human capital level increased for all countries and was key part of economies in 2005. However, human capital level decreased since then for all countries while stayed unchanged for lower middle-income countries. But still human capital is main source of GDP for countries except low income countries where natural resources dominates economy.

Table 1. HDI and its components by best and worst rankings for 2019 year

Rank	Country	HDI	Life expectancy at birth (years)	Expected years of schooling (years)	Mean year of schooling (years)	GNI per capita PPP
1	Norway	0.954	82.3	18.1	12.6	68,059
4	Hong Kong	0.939	84.7	16.5	12	60,221
4	Germany	0.939	81.2	17	14.1	46,136
6	Australia	0.938	83.3	22.1	12.7	44,097
	<i>OECD</i>	<i>0.895</i>	<i>80.4</i>	<i>16.3</i>	<i>12.0</i>	<i>40,615</i>
41	Qatar	0.848	80,1	12,2	9.7	110,489
49	Russia	0.824	72.4	15.5	12	25,036
50	Kazakhstan	0.817	73,2	15.3	11.8	22,168
87	Azerbaijan	0.754	72.9	12.4	10.5	15,240

	<i>Developing countries</i>	0.686	71.1	12.2	7.4	10,476
	<i>LDCs</i>	0.528	65	9.8	4.8	2,630
182	Burkina Faso	0.434	61.2	8.9	1.6	1,705
185	Burundi	0.423	61.2	11.3	3.1	660
187	South Sudan	0.413	57.6	5	4.8	1455
188	CAR	0.381	52.8	7.6	4.3	777
189	Niger	0.377	62	6.5	2	912

Source: UNDP, Human Development Report, 2019

Note: VERY HIGH HUMAN DEVELOPMENT ranks within 1-62, HIGH HUMAN DEVELOPMENT ranks within 63-116, MEDIUM HUMAN DEVELOPMENT ranks within 117-153, LOW HUMAN DEVELOPMENT ranks within 154-189

As can be seen from the Table 1, red marked points are highest (lowest) score of the category listed. It is obvious from the formula of global HDI and table that countries with high HDI mainly correspond with their income level as well as expected years and mean years of schooling. HDI and its components have similar line for Russia, Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan. However, schooling years higher for Russia and Kazakhstan with more pre-school start age and 12 years education.

According to *Education at a Glance 2017 by OECD*, in 2014, the U.S. spent an average of \$12,300 per student on elementary and secondary education, which is 30% more than the average spending in OECD. Among OECD, Mexico has lowest expenses by dollar and share of GDP. Expenditures on college and universities, was nearly \$30,000, 75% more than in OECD average. Nevertheless, Norway spent 15,000 US dollar in 2014 highest in OECD member countries, which increased from 12,600 US dollar since 2005. On average, such expenses increased 15% in OECD countries. However, in U.S. this indicator increased only 300 US dollar (+3%) over this period. highest spending level per student at the postsecondary education is in the United States were 81 percent higher than the OECD average of \$16,400 with 1% decrease over same period. Total U.S. spending is \$16,268 per student, 51% more than the average in OECD.

Among OECD countries with highest total education expenditures including private sector are UK (6.6% of GDP), Denmark (6.5% of GDP), New Zealand (6.4% of GDP), and US (6.2% of GDP) in 2014. However, US expenses on postsecondary education was slightly below of average in this regard.

Chart 2. Education Index of HDI by best and worst indicators, and by Azerbaijan, Russia, Kazakhstan between 1990-2019 years

Source: UNDP, Human Development Reports, 2020

Chart 2 shows us Education Indexes of Azerbaijan, Russia, Kazakhstan and Germany, Australia, Denmark, Norway as by best performances and CAR, Burkina Faso and Niger as demonstrating worst indicators for comparison between 1990-2019 years. These three analyzed countries have similar indexes in this regard whereas these indexes are between 2 polar group of countries.

Education in transition period of Post-soviet countries

In Soviet period, Higher Education Institutions were required to train a specified number of people in certain fields, while the larger economic planning system was responsible for graduates' job assignments by sectorial ministries of specific industries. Most higher education institutions were transferred from the ministry of education to various sectorial ministries and state departments (David-Fox, 2012; Ryzhkovskiy, 2012).

In 1991, the Soviet model of higher education of 15 USSR republics, with its 5.1 million students and 946 higher education institutions with at least one university by country, changed from a centrally planned organization and financing of education into globalized capitalist ruled education system. (Smolentseva, Huisman, & Froumin, 2018)

Commonly, the collapse of the centrally planned economy was associated with economic decline, political instability, a drastic drop in public funding and brain drain from higher education and research institutions to other sectors of the economy or overseas which deeply affected their societies and economies (Smolentseva et al., 2018). Newly independent nations adopted a similar package of reforms in higher education, many of these neo-liberal, like establishment of private sector, tuition fees in the public institutions, national standardized tests for admission exams to higher education, and even loans for students in some countries (Silova & Steiner-Khamsi 2008; Smolentseva 2012)

Eventually, all these states adopted higher education programmes from the Western world. Main features of these reforms were that Soviet ideological courses were excluded from curricula and higher education

programmes were supplemented by courses on national history and culture and most importantly all courses in native language.

The participation rate in higher education, calculated as a gross enrolment ratio (number of students as youth), was relatively high in the USSR in general but, Central Asian republics and Azerbaijan demonstrating relatively modest indicators (12 % for Turkmenistan, 15 % for Tajikistan, 16 % Kyrgyz Republic, 15 % for Azerbaijan).

Education profile of Russian Federation

Revenues from oil&gas revenues accounted for 46 % of all federal budget revenues in 2018 (BOFIT 2019). Oil industry play huge role in tax collection in budget. Oil price drop in 2014 had negative impact on federal tax revenues. Additively exchange rate shocks led to budget revenues fell by more than 30 % of budget resulting federal budget deficit of 3.4% of GDP in 2016. But oil price benchmark for 2019 federal budget has been increased and so budget revenues will be expected to run surplus instead of deficit (Kluge, 2019).

The Education Law of 1992 gave state, municipal, private and religious organizations the right to run educational institutions, and also legalized home schooling, breaking the state monopoly on education established by the Communists in 1918 (Zakon, 1992) The 1992 Education Law requiring compulsory education only through grade 9 was rescinded with 1994 Education Law based on idea that institutions were to be strictly non-commercial and non-profit.

To adapt Western models and practices, starting from 1993 a massive expansion of international assistance to Russian education with expanding educational exchanges funded through the U.S. government's Freedom Support Act and the European Union's TACIS program, as well as The Council of Europe in research seminars and training efforts. Additionally, Soros Foundation in Moscow played huge role in education such as 25 new textbooks that are being published in editions of 1 million each and being sold at cost to Russian schools in 1994. (Johnson, 1996)

The World Bank report on Russian education of 1995 suggests that Russian administrators, educators and teachers must be willing to reform their institutions. Proposed measures include emergency financing to protect preschool and compulsory education and ease the social costs of transition; adapting obsolete institutions and curricula to the new labor markets, and shifting away from the scientism and narrow vocationalism of traditional Soviet curricula; downsizing inflated pedagogical staffs; fostering responsible and effective decentralization through the development of regional and local management and financing; forging greater coherence between federal, regional and local functions and policies; leveraging federal funds to ensure relative equality of educational opportunity; establishing a national and meritocratic examination system; opening up and privatizing educational publishing; renewing and reforming vocational education by means of consumer and employer demand; and reforming teacher training by moving it out of the grossly-underfunded pedagogical institutes and into the state universities and the mainstream of the subject disciplines. Overall, the role of the federal government would shift from direct financing and bureaucratic control to "quality assurance and equality monitoring" (OECD, 1998; OECD 1999).

In the period of 1995-2011 years, expenditure per student by educational institutions increased in every country, especially first half of this period. However, after 2008 crisis, expenses preprimary, secondary and tertiary students in some countries including Russia. Government expenditure per primary and secondary students as % of GDP per capita started to increase in 2011. (OECD, 2014, p. 205-219).

Between 2005 and 2015, education spending fell by 0.8 percent to 2.6 percent of GDP and healthcare spending declined by 0.6 percent to 3.8 percent of GDP (CNBC, 2018)

In general, R&D expenses constitutes with economic growth and education level of society as SDG indicator. Russia is 10th country in R&D expenses which is 12.8 times less than USA ranked first in 2016 (UNESCO).

Education profile of Kazakhstan

During years 2000–2013, Kazakhstan GDP has surged almost 13-fold, but fall drastically following years 2014–2015 due to oil price slump and started to increase after 2017 (WB, 2017).

Half of the government's total revenues consist of oil revenues which is also more than two third of foreign exchange earnings in Kazakhstan in recent years. Sharp decline in oil prices, the recession in Russia, and the Kazakh economy led to several shocks caused to having spent \$ 7 bn of reserves and resulted 40% devaluation of its currency in July 2015. (BNP, 2015)

Due to oil shocks Oil Fund of Kazakhstan (NFKR) supported economy between 2014-17 years valued \$13.2 bn. The Fund offset budget cuts on economic activities owing to revenue fall and expenses growth. Meanwhile, transfers from Fund to state budget continues to grow, state budget non-oil deficit reached 4.47 bn tenge (accounted 10.8% of GDP) twice more than 2014 deficit amount. (WB 2015, Kazakhstan: Low Oil Prices; an Opportunity to Reform). For instance, transfers from NFKR to state budget accounted \$8bn as one-third of 2016 government budget., which plans to be \$7.13 bn as a quarter of budget in 2019. Transfers from the NFRK to the republican budget \$10.9 billion in 2014, increased from \$9.2 billion in 2013. Government allocations of guaranteed and targeted transfers from the NFRK to support the republican budget increased in 2015 to \$13.4 billion, 41.5% of total revenue of budget. (KFM, 2019)

Since 1991, over 100,000 students studied abroad with current 89,505 students. 477,074 students are enrolled 122 universities. Tuition fees in Kazakhstan are from \$1,000 up to \$15,000 per year, primarily with western universities style. More than 93% of the students are self-funded. Since 2011, the Bolashak ("Future") scholarship program has provided scholarships for master's and PhD programs abroad.

For insuring programs correspond to international standards, government strict licensing regulations and qualification requirements for universities and wants to limit to 100 through mergers, downgrading, and closures.

Unlike the rest of Central Asia, Kazakhstan's per-capita GDP has been steadily increasing up until 2014, creating burgeoning middle- and upper-class youth eager to travel and study abroad. However, multiple currency devaluations in 2014 as well as in 2015 had a negative impact on Kazakhstani families. Nonetheless, government policy has dramatically increased English-language education nationwide over the past decade (Export, 2019)

In 2014, 7648 schools including primary and secondary level catered more than 2.572 million pupils. Despite, private schools significantly increase recent years, take part only (107 schools) 1.4 % of all schools enrolling (19.6 thousand students) 0.8% of students (OECD, 2015)

Kazakhstan public expenses on education stood at 3.6% of GDP in 2014 where higher education expenses took one of tenth part of it with roughly \$ 400 million which is very low than OECD countries. Primary financing source of higher education is self-financing even at state institutions. Higher education accounts 1% in GDP, where private spending takes 0.7% of GDP. Government grants 30,000 students in higher education which is a quarter number of applied students (OECD, 2017).

OECD/World Bank recommendations for Kazakhstan education in 2007 had no significant change in financing sight. This report suggested to increase public education expenses in GDP and in budget up to 20% and increase tertiary education budget at least 15% of education expenses of budget. Additionally, funding for R&D still quite small (OECD, 2007). Expenditure on (primary and secondary) school education stood at 2.1% of GDP which is considerably low than OECD average of 3.6%.

Education profile in Azerbaijan

The government of Azerbaijan has set a priority to transform resource revenues into human capital that could be seen from various conceptual decrees, including the “Azerbaijan 2020: Look into the Future” vision set in 2012, the “National Strategy for the Development of Education” in 2013 which prioritizes to boost human capital development level and to escape ‘resource curse’ by improving quality of the educational system and the competitiveness of knowledge-based economy. It emphasizes on the development of competence-based education, new management mechanisms based on state-society and public-private partnerships, and the creation of lifelong learning. In March 2016, a further decree was signed for the development of strategic roadmaps for eight priority sectors that are critical for diversifying the economy, improving export competitiveness, increasing efficiency of domestic markets which included vocational education and training as one important sector (Mammadova, 2016), (MoE, 2016).

Since 2005, Azerbaijan started to gather huge oil revenues, which increased per capita GNI twice from \$8,570 in 2006 to \$16,920 in 2014. During the period of 2001–2009, GDP growth was on average 16% per year, and Azerbaijan had the highest GDP growth rate worldwide at 34.5% in 2006 and 25% in 2007. Using such revenues, government mainly invested in tangible capital such as construction and infrastructure 35% of state budget on average between 2007–2014 years. Meanwhile, Public spending on education expenses decreased from 13% to 9% in budget in this period. Government education expenses stood at 2.8% of GDP, while health expenses were just 1% of GDP on average (WB, 2010), (Mammadova, 2016)

Literacy rate among population is very high in Azerbaijan, which increased from 98.79 % in 1999 to 99.79% in 2016 ranked 2nd in the world according to UNESCO. Also, female literacy rate among youth population stayed just behind (0.04%) of male literacy rate.

As seen from Chart below, state budget of Azerbaijan Republic has been increased more than 40 times between 1995-2017 years. That increase can be seen obvious since Oil boom in 2003, including education expenses of budget. However, education expenses as percentile decreased in this period and stood at 10.2% of budget.

Chart 3. Enrollment in pre-school in Azerbaijan with world average comparison, in % and number of students

Source: Ministry of Education of Azerbaijan Republic

Unlike world average, attendance in pre-school in Azerbaijan is very low, as more than half of pupil does not enrolled in pre-school.

Chart 5. Attendance in pre-school in Azerbaijan

Source: Ministry of Education of Azerbaijan Republic

If those charts would be considered together, pre-school enrollment seems key problem for education system in Azerbaijan. However, there is tremendous progress in recent years in this field. Study of MEAR reveal that, students enrolled in pre-school demonstrate higher results in mathematics and even other subjects. Also, the more attendance in pre-school corresponds with higher score which matches world average. As seen from chart above, 46% of all students at that age already enrolled in pre-school in Azerbaijan in recent years.

However, preschool enrollment rate was higher in Russia above 80% and Kazakhstan above 50 % of all eligible children. Despite decrease trend in preprimary education in first years in these three countries, preprimary school enrollment as part of all eligible children in Russia started to increase from 60% in 2000 up to 88% in 2016 and from 20% in 2000 up to 59% in 2016 for Kazakhstan. Primary education enrollment is quite good in these countries with above 100 points in same measurement. Russia has highest tertiary enrollment level with 80% where Kazakhstan stood at 46% and Azerbaijan 27% of all eligible children for 2016 according to UNESCO statistics. In Azerbaijan, private schools take less than 1% (with 30 schools and 12000 students) of all school.

According to the study on education efficiency in Azerbaijan applying Data Envelope Analysis method, Azerbaijan’s education expenditure efficiency score of 0.29 (input oriented) is way below than regional average of 0.73, whereas health expenditure efficiency scores slightly below of region (Mammadova, S. 2016).

Comparison of education stream in these countries

Despite these countries share similar destiny in economy, social and political stance, they have different outputs. Economic structure of these countries can also be seen from the graph shown economic volume of them. As seen, dynamics of GDP output is very similar and impacts of global economic fluctuations also

common as oil prices changed. For instance, economic volume has been increased till 2008 and sharp decline in oil prices impacted all these countries after then. Started declining in oil prices in 2014 is also evidence how these countries' economies linked to oil export. Russia's economy is 9.8 times bigger than Kazakhstan and Kazakhstan economy is almost 4 times higher than Azerbaijan. Although economic profile is very similar, Azerbaijan economy seems less volatile in comparison.

Graph 6. Economic output in Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and Russia (in right axis), in billion USD, 2000-2017 years

Source: World Bank data, World Development Indicators

Russia, Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan joined to OPEC+ group since end-2016 producing with more than 14 mln barrel per day altogether (Cordell, 2019). Usage of oil revenues in current budget is very high for these countries since golden rule has not been established very strictly. Thanks to high oil prices above \$100 in 2011-2013 years share of oil revenues in Russia and Azerbaijan accounted significant. Kazakhstan could manage oil revenues countercyclical, but still oil share in their budget more than third.

Chart 7. Oil revenues in government budget in Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and Russia, %, 2009-2017 years

Source: Ministry of Finance of selected countries.

Education expenses of these countries as part of budget and economy is very common and below EU and OECD average. Education expenses as part of GDP and budget slightly decreased in Azerbaijan especially post-crisis period.

Chart 8. Education expenses as part of budget and GDP for Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and Russian Federation

Source: WB, World Development Indicators and official statistics of selected countries.

Since government overall education expenses very similar among these countries, it would be interesting to see which level of education governments care most. As we know, primary education mainly dominates by government in these countries. As seen from table below, higher education takes least portion of government education expenses, especially for Kazakhstan.

Table 2. Schooling indicators for these countries in comparison

	Literacy rate, adult, %	Population with at least secondary education 2010-2018	Expected years of schooling (SDG4.3) 2018	Pupil-teacher ratio, primary school, 2003-2018	Inequality in education, % 2018	R&D as of GDP, % 2010-2017
Russian Federation	99.7	95.9	15.5	21	3.1	1.10
Kazakhstan	99.8	98.6	15.3	20	3.2	0.14
Azerbaijan	99.8	95.6	12.4	15	5.3	0.19
OECD	-	86.2	16.3	15	8.0	2.44
World	83.0	66.7	12.7	23	22.3	2.01
Developing countries	81.9	60.1	12.2	25	25.6	1.27
LDCs	63.5	29.8	9.8	37	36.3	-

Source: UNESCO Institute for Statistics. 2019. Data Centre. <http://data.uis.unesco.org>

Table 3. Gross enrolment ratio by education level of selected countries in comparison.

	Gross enrolment ratio in pre-primary (SDG4.2) 2013-2018	Gross enrolment ratio in primary (SDG4.1) 2013-2018	Gross enrolment ratio in secondary (SDG4.1) 2013-2018	Gross enrolment ratio in tertiary (SDG4.3) 2013-2018	Expected years of schooling (SDG4.3) 2018
Russian Federation	89	102	105	82	15.5
Kazakhstan	58	105	113	53	15.3
Azerbaijan	36	103	95	27	12.4
<i>OECD</i>	80	102	107	75	16.3
<i>World</i>	51	104	79	39	12.7
<i>Developing countries</i>	45	105	75	34	12.2
<i>LDCs</i>	25	103	47	11	9.8

Source: UNESCO Institute for Statistics. 2019. Data Centre. <http://data.uis.unesco.org>

In OECD countries government expenses toward tertiary education accounted less at least 2 times than primary to post-secondary non-tertiary. (OECD, 2020) Besides education, governments should support R&D for developing economy. R&D expenses in Azerbaijan and Kazakhstan is very low in this regard and government expenses on R&D in Russia is above 1% of GDP.

Chart 10. R&D expenses as of GDP in Russia, Azerbaijan and Kazakhstan

Source: UNESCO, <http://uis.unesco.org/>

Chart 11. R&D by sectors in % and overall value in USD

Source: WB, World Development Indicators

Chart 11, expresses research and development (R&D) expenditures covering basic research, applied research, and experimental development of these countries as a percent of GDP for 2018. It shows both capital and current expenditures in the four main sectors: Business enterprise, Government, Higher education and Private non-profit. R&D.

These countries started structural reforms in western education mindset just after getting independence. Literacy level is quite high, but there are differences in education outcomes in urban and rural areas. (OECD, 2015)

Findings and remarks

Education role in HDI and development in resource-rich CIS countries, particularly Russia, Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan contributed to HDI level and economic prosperity. This paper realized that, these three countries have more common points including education sphere. Typical features of these countries can be summarized as Government dominant financing of primary and secondary education, similar level of compulsory education, literacy level, little R&D budget, similar reforms in exams, which contributed similar Education Index Level and eventually very close HDI index.

In common, all three countries started structural reforms in western education vision just getting independence; have compulsory primary and secondary education financed by government. Despite literacy level quite high, there are differences in education outcomes in urban and rural areas.

Even though, they all started reforms since 1991 and accrued huge oil revenues, these countries could not transfer such resources into HC enough, because common budget structure, like more portion went to hard infrastructure, particularly in education sphere which cannot be seen as education expenses.

For example, 3200 school built or capitally reconstructed last fifteen years in Azerbaijan. Teachers' salary used to increase to adjust to inflation level, but significantly increased around by 35% starting from 2014 by performance.

The paper concludes that, despite huge accrued oil revenues and their usage in government budget in these countries, education expenses part did not increase in last decade and still below of EU and OECD countries. However, oil revenues did let governments to invest into non-oil sector, including education sector. More than

reforms especially in salary by performance, petro-dollars went into building educational infrastructure such as schools, training centers.

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